

Szakdolgozat

Sean Paul Bergeron

Deep multimodal transformers trained on vlogs reveal emergent group personalities during collaborative interactions

EÖTVÖS LORÁND TUDOMÁNYEGYETEM

FACULTY OF INFORMATICS

DEPARTMENT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Author:

Sean Paul Bergeron

Computer Science MSc – Artificial Intelligence Specialization

Supervisor:

Dr. András Lőrincz

Head of NIPG

Contents

1	Abstract	2
2	Introduction	3
3	Related Works	5
4	Technology Components	12
5	Analysis of Results	16
5.1	Calculation of the Average	16
5.2	Peaks in the Temporal Data	16
5.3	PCA	17
5.4	UMAP	18
5.5	Plasticity vs. Stability	20
A	Plots and Figures	24
	Bibliography	32
	List of Figures	36

Chapter 1

Abstract

Group selection has emerged during evolution. In this case, natural selection acts at the level of the group. It manifests itself during group interactions, a regular part of daily life. Almost every aspect of a person's life is affected by collaborating with other people. As it is such an important dynamic, so too is the ability to quantify it. Although groups in settings such as the workplace may be quantified by their task success, other kinds of groups do not have such a metric. Traditionally psychologists have defined the Big Five Personality Traits by which to classify individual behavior. The hypothesis is that during interaction such traits may appear at the group level and "group personality" may emerge. This work will introduce a method for quantifying groups in two-dimensional space. Features extracted from source separated speech, raw video, and transcripts will be input to a linear multimodal transformer to output a per-person personality estimation. The 5-dimensional personality points have high correlations and can be projected into two combinations, to the dimensions of "stability" and "plasticity". I used the ELEA database, a putative 'winter survival task' for my studies. Results show unique group-level personality emerges in most of the cases.

Chapter 2

Introduction

Dyadic and group interactions are complex processes. A myriad of features and metrics may be defined in an attempt to describe such a complex process.

Although interaction is a group dynamic, certain features must be viewed on an individual level. For example, features derived from speech such as prosody are more informative when taken from an individual's speech. As group interactions are by definition an exchange between more than one person, this precipitates the need for tools that isolate the speech of a given speaker from the overall conversation. The problem of isolating the speech of a single speaker from a larger group or noisy context is known as the cocktail party problem. The isolated speech may be processed to obtain low-level features or even be used in other pipelines such as automatic speech recognition. Low-level acoustic features can act as inputs to deep learning networks or even be used as indicators for hotspots in the conversation (i.e. interruptions or periods of emotional exchange). Sentiment analysis can be applied to the transcript derived from speech separation and ASR.

Other features that can describe a conversation such as gaze direction, blinking rate, and body pose are simpler to extract for the individual. Although a feature may be easy to extract for an individual, it might be more informative when considered in relation to features of the other participants. For example, the comparison of gaze directions can indicate the current center of attention in the conversation. This highlights the concept that certain features and metrics must be engineered and analyzed on a group level in order to be meaningful when describing a conversation.

Certain group-level features may even be emergent, driven by the content of the interaction and of the participants themselves. Certain features may be indicators of people driving the conversation. Features of these last two categories are more intangible than

the previously discussed interaction metrics and would usually require the annotations of a trained psychologist. Personality features include dominance, leadership, stability, plasticity, as well as the Big Five personality traits (openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeability, and neuroticism).

This work will utilize features (audio, visual, and textual) on an individual level in order to quantify group-level behavior. The choice of features necessitated the integration of audio-visual speaker source separation.

Chapter 3

Related Works

The ELEA dataset [1] is the foundation for this work. The corpus consists of 21 four person teams and 6 three person teams which were each given the same task. This winter survival task asked the participants to assume the roles of plane crash survivors. Prior to the group work each individual was given 12 items to rank in importance from most to least important to their survival. Afterwards the group as a whole was recorded with two cameras (one for each side of the table) and a central microphone as they worked to decide on a group ranking of the 12 items. The average discussion length was 14.61 minutes.

For all videos, the audio and video were synced and the resultant delay was recorded. Speaker segmentation is provided for every group with the start and end time in seconds, the subject's letter ID, and the sector assigned by the Micronone microphone. This segmentation was automatically performed by the Micronone which, for every spatial segment in its six segment array, uses a basic filter-sum beamformer followed by post-filtering.

Additional annotations are also provided. A Big Five personality score was assigned to each speaker according to a self-reported questionnaire. Furthermore, each individual was given a perceived leadership and dominance score from the rankings of the group members after the task was completed.

Conversations are complex. A myriad of higher level features can be derived from a conversation including interruption predictions and engagement level classification. However low-level descriptors can be just as informative.

Prosody is one of the most important features used in the classification and analysis of conversations. Analysis of prosodic cues, without any other feature, is often times sufficient to analyze a conversation. Wrede et al. used only prosodic features to locate hotspots,

periods where participants are highly involved in the conversation (i.e. arguments, interruptions, excitement) [2]. They concluded that there are significant differences in both the F0 and energy between involved and non-involved utterances.

Other groups have demonstrated that using only prosodic features as inputs to a deep learning network is sufficient for predicting higher level actions. Skantze et al. used voice activity, pitch, power, spectral stability, and part-of-speech as inputs to a LSTM in order to predict turn-taking in conversations [3].

Prosodic features are especially important when classifying or predicting interruptions during conversations. Lee et al. utilized the energy and pitch of the interrupted party as well as gesture features of the interrupting party (mouth opening distances, first-order polynomial parametrization for right and left eyebrows, and six degrees of rigid head motion) in order to predict interruptions with a Hidden Condition Random Field for 70% accuracy [4].

Interruption types are naturally classified by listeners using only the prosody of the speech. Past studies have found that incoming speech overlaps with higher pitch and intensity are perceived as more competitive and interruptive in nature [5]. However, as most of recent research ignores listener variability, Hilton et al. conducted a perception experiment with 500 people to determine listener attitudes of overlapping speech. They concluded that although listener personalities may modulate their perception, prosodic prominence of an incoming interruption has a significant effect on the interruption's perceived competitiveness. The results of this study demonstrate that prosodic prominence significantly affects a listener's evaluation of overlapping speech which is then mediated by the listener's own interactional style and personality.

Individual prosodic features as opposed to the group's speech are often of interest. Furthermore isolation of individual speech segments enables a neural network that is trained on videos from individual speakers to be applied to group contexts. Several approaches to speaker separation exist. The most robust systems make use of both audio and visual modalities [6]. The output of the network is also a key design choice. Either a mask or an output spectrogram may be provided.

Two different methodologies were considered for speaker separation, a series of papers by Ariel Ephrat, from the Hebrew University of Jerusalem, and a series of papers by Triantafyllos Afouras from the University of Oxford.

Ephrat's first paper detailed an end-to-end model based on CNNs which take as input silent video frames of a speaker and dense optical flow fields, returning a linear-scale spec-

trogram of the predicted speech [7]. Ephrat expanded on this work by using the predicted speech spectrogram as a mask [8]. A spectrogram is generated for each speaker by the aforementioned CNN-based network (separate network trained per speaker) and for each timestamp and frequency a binary mask is generated by comparing the generated spectrograms of the speakers. Ephrat progressed with a more robust fusion network that considers more input modalities. In [9], visual streams (one stream per speaker with shared weights) take as input per frame facial embeddings and learn a visual feature embedding using dilated convolutions. The audio stream takes the spectrogram of the mixed speech and then learns an audio feature embedding using dilated convolutions. The learned audio and visual features are concatenated and processed with a bidirectional LSTM followed by fully connected layers which output a complex spectrogram mask for each speaker.

Afouras posited an entirely different approach by separately predicting the magnitude and the phase of the isolated speaker [10] using two different sub-networks. The magnitude subnetwork takes as input the magnitude spectrogram of the original signal and the speaker video, providing a mask that upon element-wise multiplication returns a filtered magnitude spectrogram. This magnitude prediction is provided along with the phase spectrogram of the original signal to the phase subnetwork. The phase subnetwork predicts a phase residual which is added to the original phase to return the final, predicted phase.

Afouras expanded on this work by using learned audio-visual embeddings as the inputs to his previous model [11]. Trained with self-supervised learning, a model uses attention to localize sound sources and uses optical flow to aggregate information over time, transforming a video into a set of discrete audio-visual objects.

The video encoder, a spatio-temporal VGG-M network (initial 3D convolutional layer followed by cascaded 2D convolutions), extracts a video embedding of dimensionality $T \times h \times w \times D$. An audio encoder (also VGG-M architecture) outputs a D -dimensional embedding for every frame. The three dimensional (x, y , and t) attention map is calculated per timestamp by computing the cosine similarity between the video feature at each pixel (x, y) and the audio feature for that timestamp. Integration is needed to remove sporadic sounds and to sync sound sources across multiple frames. A 2-dimensional (x, y) map is output where, at each pixel location, is the score of that pixel's trajectory over the time dimension.

Identification of a discrete audio-visual object is conducted by detecting peaks in the temporally integrated 2-dimensional map, Peaks are indexed in a decreasing order and suppression is applied in a $\rho \times \rho$ area around the peak.

In order to extract the audio-visual features the sound source must be localized in each frame. For timestamp t , the tracked location $T(x, y, t)$ is used to provide an initial guess whereby the pixel location with the largest attention value is picked from within a $\rho \times \rho$ area around the initial guess. The spatial feature corresponding to the tracked source is extracted from the visual feature map.

Three main choices remained for the final speaker separation network to be used on ELEA: the "Looking to Listen" model representing the culmination of Ephrat's work, the "avobjects" pipeline representing the culmination of Afouras' work, and finally "Visual Speech Enhancement" [12] which is an offshoot project by Aviv Gabbay from Ephrat's main work.

The metrics by which these works were judged include three studies over-viewing the speech separation literature: a holistic overview of supervised speech separation methods [6], an overview of the different training targets for supervised training of separation networks [13], and finally an overview of the masking types used as training targets [14].

"Visual Speech Enhancement" was removed from consideration for two main reasons. The phase of the noisy signal is used as an approximation of the clean phase and to reconstruct the cleaned signal. The final network output is a spectrogram as opposed to a mask that may be applied to the original signal. Both review papers, [13] and [6], emphasize that using a multiplicative mask as a training target consistently provides better results than when the spectrogram itself is directly predicted.

"Looking to Listen" was recreated according to the original paper and performed well in the simplest task of isolating a single speaker from a single speaker and non-speech noise mixture. However, the network was unable to isolate a single speaker from a mixture of two or more speakers. The spectrograms cleaned by outputs masks were too similar between the two speakers. Upon inspection it was clear that the network would output very similar masks for both speakers that would attenuate the louder speaker in the mixture. The suspected reason for this error was the usage of facial recognition embeddings as inputs to the visual stream of the network. Facial recognition embeddings are trained to only preserve necessary information, discarding variation between images, including variation between images of the same person. Facial expression and lip orientation would therefore be discarded in the embedding.

The visual information in audio-visual networks is key for the network's assignment of the output channels to the face of the corresponding speaker. This is the reason why audio only models require the use of permutation-invariant training targets [15]. The use

of facial recognition embeddings may lose key information that inhibits proper assignment of the output channels during training which would cause the network to have poor performance. Then the only use case without an error would be the removal of non-speech noise.

This open question along with several other ambiguities in the original paper that could not be answered caused this approach to be abandoned. The "avobjects" pipeline along with its separation module [10] addressed all the above shortcomings of the other two approaches. At no point in either sub-network is a spectrogram directly predicted. The visual features provided to the magnitude sub-network are extracted from the video images using a spatio-temporal residual network pre-trained on a word-level lip reading task. In this case visual information used by the network is directly related to the mechanisms of speech and lip movements as opposed to a more general face recognition embedding.

A key conclusion of the review of mask types conducted by Wang et al. is that the phase is more important especially in combination with the magnitude masks and less important in the absence of magnitude enhancement [14]. The hypothesis that there is structure in speech which produces a correlation between the magnitude and phase spectrograms is integral to the design of the phase sub-network in Afouras' work. This is why both the magnitude prediction and the noisy phase are projected and concatenated before being processed by the temporal convolutional blocks in the phase sub-network.

The separated speech is needed for the multimodal linear attention personality estimation network. The network was trained on clips from more than 3000 different YouTube videos of individuals facing the camera in a vlog-like manner. A single person speaks in a single clip.

The network utilizes a multimodal attention network [16] with linear complexities [17]. The linear multimodal attention network was trained on the First Impressions V2 dataset [18]. The output of the network is a 5-dimensional vector projected to the range of 0 to 1 representing the Big Five personality traits. The modalities input to the network include acoustic, visual, and textual features.

Low-level audio descriptors are extracted from the separated speech signal including the slope V0, spectral flux, MFCC, loudness, F0 semitone, alpha ratio, shimmer, jitter, Hammarberg index, F1, F2, and F3. This feature set is known as the extended Geneva Minimalistic Acoustic Parameter Set (eGeMAPS) [19] and was extracted using openSMILE [20].

The visual features are associated with facial expression and movement. Special care

is taken not to introduce bias by removing other kinds of information. The features include Action Units (AU) [21] extracted by OpenFace [22] and deep features extracted by FAb-Net [23]. Action Units encode both the presence and intensity of facial expressions as categorized by the Facial Action Code System. The FAb-Net architecture was trained to encode the pose, emotions, and landmarks associated with a facial expression.

The textual features are extracted by BERT [24] and RoBERTa [25]. BERT applies the bidirectional training of a transformer to language modeling in order to learn contextual relations between words. A 768-dimensional word embedding is returned from a transcript. The robustly optimized BERT approach, RoBERTa, makes improvements over BERT by using the Masked Language Modeling objective when trained on unannotated large scale datasets. This model extracts a 1024-dimensional textual embedding.

During a conversation, it is useful to define a metric by which to describe the behavior and personality of individuals. One of the most widely accepted personality trait organizations is the 5-dimensional Big Five model. John Digman unified several theories and defined the five factors as openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism [26]. Furthermore he used factor correlations from 14 studies to identify another two higher order factors known as alpha and beta [27]. Alpha, or stability, is an aggregate of agreeableness, conscientiousness, and emotional stability (the inverse of neuroticism). Beta, or plasticity, is defined as an aggregate of extraversion and openness.

Although its useful to define personality with just two high-level factors, it must also be proved that these factors are not too general and may be used to explain specific trends in human behaviors. Otherwise extraction of said factors would be meaningless in describing interactions.

Jang et al. [28] conducted a factorial analysis of the responses to the Revised NEO Personality Inventory by 1209 MZ and 701 DZ twins from Japan, Canada, and Germany. Not only did the analysis result in two factors similar to alpha and beta, but the factor structure itself mirrored the structural effects of several genetic influences. This links Digman's factors to developmental theory.

DeYoung et al. [29] reproduced the higher-order factors in a university and community sample while relating both factors to a biological model that regulates the functioning of serotonin and dopamine. In both sample sets they concluded that the act of conforming in social situations is positively related to stability and negatively related to plasticity. This supports the conclusion that higher order factors do indeed describe the impact of personality on inter-personal interactions in meaningful ways.

Hirsch et al. [30] expanded on this work, claiming that the two metatraits can be used to describe and characterize the extent to which individuals will regulate their own behavior in interactions. As shown by DeYoung et al., the metatraits relate to the functionality of serotonin and dopamine. Serotonin is associated with satisfaction and restraint while dopamine is associated with exploration and action. As hypothesized, when looking at the self-reports and behavioral tasks of 307 adults, the frequencies of these acts were found to be positively correlated with plasticity and negatively with stability. This implies that the value of an individual's plasticity or stability may describe and even predict how they act in group interactions. For example, a higher plasticity individual may self-regulate less and therefore cause more interruptions or would attempt to take leadership of the conversation.

It is clear that extraction of higher-level features may be used to explain specific trends in individual persons. As demonstrated in the case of stability and plasticity, only two dimensions are needed to make predictions on individual behavior. This begs the question; can the description of behavior with higher-level factors be extended to groups?

The work of Barsade and Knight [31] reviewed the relevant literature on group affect, defined as "collective-level affective constructs" such as emotion on a group level. There is a general consensus among psychologists that affect in groups is more disposed towards uniformity. Possible causes as to why the individual affective states of people working together will converge include: emotional contagion, attraction-similarity-attrition, and shared affective experiences.

Unlike to group affect, group personality has not been as widely studied and understood. Often times researchers will settle for using the average of self-assessments when defining group personality. It will be proven that similar to the individual, group personality may be directly measured using the factors of stability and plasticity derived from a multi-modal deep-learning personality estimation network.

Chapter 4

Technology Components

An official implementation of Afouras' "avobjects" was made public but modification was needed in order to process videos from the ELEA database. The computational load of processing longer (~15 min) videos necessitated the application of the network on smaller 15 second chunks. As this network discovers audio-visual objects without considering speaker identity, it was necessary to develop a means of synchronizing speaker identities across the inference outputs. The identification and synchronization required the use of facial recognition.

Facial recognition is applied using the `face_recognition` library in python. For a video, the first frame (or images provided by the user) are used to create the facial identity encodings. Each frame in the clip is processed to return the location of the detected speakers in the frame. However, a frame is not included if the wrong number of faces is detected, if the faces are detected below a set confidence threshold, or if two (or more) detected faces are assigned to the same identity. Thus a trajectory over the clip for each individual is generated using face locations from all valid frames.

Synchronization of audio-visual objects between video chunks was made possible by no longer greedily choosing peaks in the time-averaged audio-visual attention map but instead by choosing the largest peaks that correspond to facial recognition and tracking. The more sophisticated approach is to take the trajectory calculated using facial tracking and, for each peak in the integrated attention map, compare it to the trajectory generated by tracking the sound source of the peak in each frame (already conducted in the extraction of feature embeddings). Comparison of the two time series could be done via DTW or ARIMA. However, the individuals in the ELEA videos are seated so it's sufficient to simply take the average face location and compare it to the peaks in the attention map

which is already time-averaged. Of the largest peaks in the integrated attention map, the two peaks (two speakers are shown in every ELEA video) with the smallest Euclidean distance from the averaged face locations are chosen. The features associated with these peaks are then used for speech separation.

Each video in the ELEA database was processed using this pipeline to return the separated speech of every speaker. Audio features were extracted from this separated speech. Visual features were extracted from the raw video. Textual features were extracted from the transcripts provided by the authors as opposed to automatic speech recognition on the separated speech. The features extracted were detailed in Chapter 3. The features were input to the linear multimodal transformer to obtain a 5-dimensional prediction at each timestamp for each speaker. Inference on ELEA and training of the linear multimodal transformer were conducted by Adam Fodor, a PhD student at NIPG.

In order to determine how predicted personality metrics are influenced by interruptions, all interruptions were automatically detected. This requires an automatic overlap detector. Overlapped speech is defined as segments where at least two speakers are speaking at the same time. There are different categories of overlapping speech as well. Overlapping speech may be classified as competitive interruptions, cooperative interruptions, and back channels [32].

Cooperative interruptions are when the interrupting party interjects in support of the subject or message of the current speaker. This kind of interruption doesn't always end in a change of speaker.

Back channels are two or one syllable words such as "yeah", "of course", or "got it" that don't alter the flow of conversation. These parts of overlapped speech are not of interest because they neither change the speaking floor nor do they change the topic of the conversation. Back channels are usually done in a supporting role, showing the speaker that the listener is attending to their message and is communicating their understanding while allowing the speaker to continue speaking.

The package used for overlap detection is pyannote-audio [33] which implements a model with architecture from Bullock et al. [34] trained on the AMI meeting corpus [35]. The architecture from Bullock et al. achieved state-of-the-art accuracy on AMI and ETAPE. The model consists of a trainable, feature-extraction head of SincConv layers followed by convolutional layers. The features are passed to two stacked bi-directional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) recurrent layers which is followed by a final 2-unit classification layer with softmax activation. If the output is above a threshold it indicates

that more than one speaker is talking. Training was conducted on 2-second segments. At inference time a sliding window provides several overlapping prediction scores that are averaged for a given time step.

This method was chosen for its use of SincConv layers which removes the need to use hand-crafted features [36]. The SincConv layer is based on parameterized sinc functions that act as band-pass filters, learning the low and high cutoff frequency parameters. In the end the network will be able to better extract narrow-band features such as formants and pitch.

This training data closely relates to the conditions of the ELEA corpus. The AMI meeting corpus consists of either meetings where participants act out roles in a design team from incubation to release or naturally occurring meetings spanning a range of disciplines. This ensures that the network will perform well upon inference since the data it's trained on (AMI) is similar to ELEA.

The limitations introduced by training the network on two second chunks is not a liability because a resolution of less than two seconds is unnecessary. Short back channels are not of interest for analysis, just interruptions (both cooperative and competitive).

For each group in the ELEA database, the raw audio of the group is given to the PyanNet architecture trained on the AMI corpus. Each output is post-processed using the built-in Binarize() function in pyannote-audio which binarizes predictions using onset and offset thresholding for the detection of the beginning and end of an overlapping speech segment. If the network output is larger than the onset threshold then the overlap switches from inactive to active and when the network output is less than the offset threshold then the overlap period switches from active to inactive.

The thresholds must be tuned from the default settings (0.55 for both thresholds). Hyperparameter tuning was conducted by processing the same audio for several different threshold values (grid search). For each value, the detected overlap segments were manually analyzed. For example, setting a value of 0.26 for both thresholds extends the duration of predicted overlaps past the actual overlap duration and classifies back channels as actual overlaps. Setting a value of 0.75 for both thresholds will shorten the duration of detected overlaps and will cause certain short overlaps to not be properly detected.

In the case of ELEA, the overlap detection network was classifying too many back channels as overlaps. Several solutions were considered such as excluding overlaps with a duration less than n seconds or excluding overlaps whose corresponding transcript line is less than n syllables. The former approach was used as the transcripts were not reliable and

important overlaps do not always depend on the number of words/syllables. The threshold values were set higher to 0.75 and all overlap segments with a duration less than 3 seconds were discarded. This ensured that back channels were not returned as valid overlapping segments.

After all valid overlapping segments were found for a group, for each overlap segment, all lines in the segmentation file were iterated over. The line in the segmentation file whose start time is closest to the overlapped speech start time is flagged as a possible interrupting speaker. All subsequent segmentation lines whose duration intersects with the overlapped segment duration are saved as associated speakers. A csv file was generated where each line corresponds to an overlapped speech segment and includes the possible interrupting speaker as well as the associated speakers. This distinction was made as after an interruption other speakers may decide to try and take the floor while the original speaker may also still be talking in an effort to retain the speaking floor. An aggregate score may now be taken for each speaker by counting the number of times they either interrupt or are associated with an interruption during the course of the task. This aggregate overlap score may then be related to the higher order personality factors that were previously discussed to affect interpersonal behavior.

Chapter 5

Analysis of Results

5.1 Calculation of the Average

Each speaker in the ELEA database may be represented as a point in 5-dimensional space. This point is obtained by averaging over the entire length of the video. For each person, extracted via linear multimodal transformer, is a Big Five trajectory computed using a 3s sliding window. At each timestamp in the trajectory, if the visual feature is detected above a confidence threshold of 0.6 and the person is actively speaking, then the point is added to a list for the speaker. The speaker average is taken by averaging all collected points for a speaker over the length of the video. Once an average point in 5-dimensional space is obtained for every speaker in every group, the N-speaker by 5-dimensional matrix may be standardized by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance.

5.2 Peaks in the Temporal Data

Initial analysis of the behavioral trajectories extracted by the linear multimodal transformer did not yield useful information. A new group-level temporal signal was extracted. At each timestamp, the deviation of each valid speaker (active speaker and visual feature available) from his/her average is taken and the absolute value of the deviations are summed for all active speakers. This provides a 5-dimensional series, $B(t)$ where each dimension relates to group aggregated changes in a different Big Five trait. See the following equations where i and j represent the Big Five index and speaker index respectively:

$$D_{i,j}(t) = d_{i,j}(t) - a_{i,j} \quad (5.1)$$

$$B_i(t) = \sum_j |D_{i,j}(t)| \quad (5.2)$$

Manual inspection of the largest peaks in this trajectory show that the peaks correspond to a "hotspot", be it a short interruption which yields a change in the speaking floor (not registered by the overlapping speech detector due to brevity), longer periods of overlapped speech, or laughter. Extraction of the video segments corresponding to these peaks may be used to generate a data set for fine-tuning the transformer and improving its performance on the new dataset. Furthermore, these peaks could be combined with tools such as blink and gesture detection to consistently and automatically mark hotspots in conversation.

5.3 PCA

After obtaining an average point for each speaker, the average vector is simply the directional distance from the origin to the speaker's point in 5-dimensional space. Then, for each speaker, the collected speaking points are centered by subtracting the mean [37]. The centered speaking points are used to calculate the covariance matrix whose eigenvectors represent the principle components for the distribution of the speaker's points in five-dimensional space.

Several metrics may be analyzed including the relative importance of the eigenvectors, the angle between the first principle component and the average vector, as well as the L2 norm of the average vector. The relative importance of a principle component is the percent of variance retained in that direction. The relative importance of the first principle component ranged from 60.19 (speaker 24_L) to 84.9 (speaker 24_N). For all speakers, the majority of the variance is explained by the first principle component. Without mean-centering the data, the first component usually points in the direction of the average [37]. Because the data was mean-centered, the angle between the first component and the average vector was calculated. The angle was never orthogonal for any speaker, instead only taking on a value of near 150 or 20.

5.4 UMAP

The UMAP, or Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction [38], algorithm may be used to reduce the dimensionality of a dataset. In this case, UMAP is used to project each person's average in 5 dimensional space to 2 dimensional space in order to better cluster and visualize the data. The projection obtained via UMAP depends on two key parameters: the minimum distance and the number of neighbors. More specifically, the minimum distance apart that points are allowed to be in the lower dimensional representation. The number of neighbors constrains the size of the local neighborhood UMAP will look at when attempting to learn the manifold structure of the data.

Several configurations of the two hyperparameters were tested via grid search. In all cases, three distinct clusters are visible. Changing the hyperparameters only changes the relative positioning of these clusters in the new 2 dimensional space. Behavior within a cluster is not affected by these hyperparameters. Thus final values used were 0.0 for minimum distance and 10 for the number of neighbors.

The UMAP projection to two dimensions of every ELEA speaker's average may be view in Figure A1. The points are color-coded according to the number of overlapping speech segments (not overall duration) a speaker participated in during the their session. Lighter colors correspond to more participation in overlapped speech segments. The lightest colored point for the entire dataset corresponds to speaker N in group 30. This individual raises his tone and continues talking over anyone that attempts to interrupt or take the speaking floor from him. The smallest cluster, the blue cluster in Figure A4, also happens to have the most light colored points. The remaining light colored points in the smallest, blue cluster correspond to group 25 (speakers L, K, and N). The two new dimensions are not correlated with dominance and leadership as seen in Figures A2 and A3.

The UMAP projected data, clustered via KMeans, may be viewed in Figure A4. In general, all speakers in a group tend to belong to the same cluster. However, for 12 of the groups this is not the case. For these 12 groups, only one speaker is assigned to a different cluster. The remaining speakers stay together in the same cluster. The outlier speaker is not on the border between clusters. There is clear separation. This is visible in Figure A5. Each subplot in Figures A5 corresponds to a group where this outlier behavior is observed. In red is the outlier, in green are the group points in the same cluster, and in blue are all speakers not in the given group.

The cluster assignments are as follows:

Cluster 1 - Red

12-K, 12-L, 12-M, 12-N, 14-M, 14-N, 14-L, 16-K, 16-L, 16-N, 16-M
17-L, 17-K, 21-N, 22-N, 24-K, 24-M, 24-N, 26-L, 26-K, 28-N, 30-K
36-K, 36-L, 38-L, 38-M, 38-N, 39-M, 39-L, 39-N

Cluster 2 - Green

14-K, 17-M, 21-L, 21-K, 21-M, 22-K, 22-L, 22-M, 23-L, 23-M,
24-L, 26-M, 26-N, 28-L, 28-K, 28-M, 32-L, 32-M, 32-K, 34-N
34-K, 36-M, 38-K, 39-K

Cluster 3 - Blue

23-K, 25-K, 25-N, 25-L, 25-M, 30-N, 30-L, 30-M, 34-M, 34-L

Given these cluster assignments, the speakers that display the aforementioned outlier behavior are:

14-K, 17-L, 21-N, 22-N, 23-K, 24-L, 26-L, 28-N, 30-K, 36-M, 38-K, 39-K

The reason for the outlier behavior was investigated. The first check was to ensure that the outlier was not simply the speaker with the least number of speaking points and/or successful visual feature capture frames. There was no correlation found between outlier behavior and the speaker with the least number of valid speaking points.

Previously calculated metrics such as the angle between the average and first principle direction vectors, the L2 norm of the average vector, the number of interruptions participated in, and the perceived leadership and dominance scores were considered. No correlation was found between outlier behavior and the angle magnitude. In 5 of the 12 groups the outlier was also the speaker with the least or most participation in interruption episodes (21_N, 23_K, 24_L, 30_K, 36_M). In 5 of the 12 groups (14_K, 22_N, 24_L, 26_L, 30_K) the outlier was also the speaker with the greatest value in either perceived dominance or leadership. In 2 of the 12 groups (23_K, 28_N) the outlier was also the speaker with the smallest value in either perceived dominance or leadership. None

of these associations apply to the majority of the groups with outlier behavior. However, one criteria held for all groups with outliers; the L2 norm of the outlier speaker's average vector was either the smallest or largest in its group.

Although the common feature that drives the speakers into clusters is not known, the clustered behavior is clear when considering UMAP projections. In this case non-linear statistical evaluation cannot surpass groupings made by a trained psychologist. Because most members in a group belong to the same cluster, this approach has potential for being a quantitative descriptor of group personality. Secondary analysis by trained psychologists would be needed to discern the difference between the clusters. The ability to identify a speaker which may differ from the group personality is shown in this work. The speaker whose L2 norm of the average vector is an extrema relative to the group may be an outlier from the group personality. Thus future steps include behavioral profiling of the outliers found in this work. The next features to be considered show greater potential for quantifying group personality.

5.5 Plasticity vs. Stability

Two additional measures, stability and plasticity, may be obtained from the standardized N-speaker by 5-dimensional matrix. Stability and plasticity are defined as follows:

$$\text{stability} = \text{agreeableness} + \text{conscientiousness} + \text{emotional stability} \quad (5.3)$$

$$\text{plasticity} = \text{extraversion} + \text{openness} \quad (5.4)$$

The corresponding columns of the aforementioned matrix are summed by these equations to obtain a new N-speaker by 2-dimensional matrix. When plotted in Figure A6, a positive linear relationship is shown between stability and plasticity. Furthermore, the points may be color-coded according to the number of overlapping speech segments (not overall duration) a speaker participated in during their session. It is clear in Figure A6 that a speaker with more overlapping speech segments will have both a greater stability value and plasticity value. The fitter library in python was used to extract a distribution for the stability data and for the plasticity data. The library checks 80 distributions from Scipy and returns the distribution with the smallest sum of square errors. The best fit dis-

tributions for stability and plasticity were a double gamma continuous distribution and a Laplace distribution respectively. Both distributions are Gaussian-like distributions.

From manual inspection of the stability-plasticity plots it can be seen in Figures A15 and A16 that the members in a group are clustered closer together than if three or four points were randomly sampled from the distribution over all the speakers. Because the ideal distributions were found to be near Gaussian, a 2D Gaussian was fit to the overall stability-plasticity data to test this hypothesis. The 2-dimensional stability-plasticity data was transposed to return the design matrix where each column is an instance, denoted as \tilde{X} . The covariance matrix is defined as follows:

$$C = \frac{1}{N} * \tilde{X} \tilde{X}^T \quad (5.5)$$

Given the covariance matrix, the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix will be denoted by V , and the covariance matrix of the projected data will be denoted by \tilde{C} . The projected data is the data projected along the two principle directions or eigenvectors (columns of V)

$$\tilde{C} = V^T C V \quad (5.6)$$

A 2D Gaussian is fitted using the covariance matrix in the rotated dimensions and the mean. The generated points are rotated by projecting onto the first two principle directions. A visualization of this fitted distribution is shown in Figure A14. It must be proven that, in the space of these two metatraits, members of a group are more similar to each other than members in a group drawn from the distribution. This will be proven by comparing the average of the standard deviation values for all of the four member groups to that of 100 groups randomly generated by the distribution. For the actual groups this value was found to be 1.33 in stability and 1.04 in plasticity. For the 100 randomly generated groups it was found to be 2.13 in stability and 1.50 in plasticity.

It must also be proven that the average of a group's speakers in stability-plasticity space differs greatly from group to group. Instead of a random distribution where the group averages will be near the mean, factors in the conversation result in a unique point in 2D space, the emergent group personality. This will be proven by comparing the standard deviation of the averages for all of the four member groups to that of 100 groups randomly generated from the distribution. For the actual groups this value was found to be 2.39 in stability and 1.55 in plasticity. For the 100 randomly generated groups it was found to be

1.48 in stability and 1.02 in plasticity. The personality of a group is emergent and distinct.

From this statistical analysis it follows that the speakers in the ELEA database are not distributed at random. Instead the spread between group members is less than the spread of the overall population. Group members are more similar to each other than to other speakers. If the group averages are compared, they do not clump near the mean of the fitted distribution but instead take a unique value in the stability and plasticity space. The subplots for groups 12 and 25 in Figure A15 demonstrate this behavior perfectly where all group members are located at an one extreme in the stability and personality space. Group members are not necessarily homogeneous but they share a emergent personality which is unique to that group its conditions. A group may be quantitatively defined according to its average value in the stability and plasticity space. This implies that groups may be directly compared by calculating the distances between their averages.

It is important to consider the factors that affect the emergent group personality such as the rate of interruptions. As seen in Figure A6, stability and plasticity are positively correlated with the sum of an individual's interruptions. Theoretically this is supported by [30] which proved that higher values of plasticity correlate with action and exploration. An individual who is prone to interrupting may influence the position of group personality in the stability and plasticity space by driving the emergent personality towards larger values. Future works may identify and analyze other factors that determine the emergent personality measured in this work.

The results of this work contribute to an understudied field. There does not yet exist a consensus among psychological researchers on the exact characteristics and nature of emergent group personality. As recently as five years ago, Allen et al. initially set out to prove that the evidence for emergent group-level constructs is minimal but instead came to the opposite conclusion [39]. Over 20 years of research on group meetings in different settings was analyzed. Although the conditions of the selected studies were diverse, Allen et al. were able to make comparisons by using the intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) and within-group agreement as the common statistics by which to determine the existence of group constructs. They found that group traits emerge as quickly as 15 to 20 minutes and change little over time. This finding implies that the validity of classifying emergent group personality in stability and plasticity with linear multimodal transformers is likely to extend to longer videos even though the average length of the videos from the ELEA database are approximately 15 minutes.

Group-level personality, when used as a feature for further analysis, is typically de-

fined in terms of a composite measure of personality scores defined for the individual. This includes metrics such as the mean, maximum, minimum, and variance. Such a composite score is different than a score that is measured holistically in the context of an interaction. The latter method contains more meaningful information as shown by Willcox et al. [40].

Using Artificial Swarm Intelligence (ASI), Willcox et al. computed the group personality of college students working on team projects. The ASI method allows each individual to influence the magnitude and direction of a graphical puck whose final location corresponds to an answer for a questionnaire. Artificial Swarm Intelligence allows group members to collaborate continuously in real-time, thus extracting a score that reflects the emergent dynamics of the group. The research team extracted the group personality score for each of the 94 small teams using both aggregates of individual Big Five inventories as well as the ASI method. When both types of group personality scores were correlated to team performance metrics (e.g. satisfaction, potency, supervisor rating, and cohesiveness), a 25% improvement was found in the correlation between team performance and the ASI survey when compared to the individual survey. Similarly, the computation of the factors of stability and plasticity is based on the measurement of the group dynamics over time. Thus these higher level factors encode more meaningful information than the baseline composite of self-report values.

Group personality is a useful high-level feature for deep networks that predict a group outcome. In a group performance classification task, Zhong et al. [41] predicted group performance using an attention-based Interlocutor Acoustic Network (IAN) whose weights are modified with a personality composite score. The final prediction is the output of a decision-level fusion between the IAN and a fully-connected network that processes the personality composite score. The authors found a 7% increase in unweighted average recall when the personality network is added to the IAN. The work of Zhong et al. did not consider the emergent personality but instead used a composite of individual scores. If a simple composite provides a boost in accuracy, then a measured emergent group personality score, such as stability and plasticity, has the potential to greatly improve the accuracy of such deep networks.

Future works could compare stability and plasticity encoded group personality derived from the linear multimodal transformer to the composite baseline. Specifically, measuring the change in accuracy of group classification tasks using the emergent stability and plasticity as modulating input features as well as computing the correlation between group outcomes and emergent stability and plasticity.

Appendix A

Plots and Figures

Figure A.1: Interruption Color-coded UMAP of Speaker Averages

Figure A.2: Dominance Color-coded UMAP of Speaker Averages

Figure A.3: Leadership Color-coded UMAP of Speaker Averages

Figure A.4: KMeans Clustering of UMAP Projected Speaker Averages

Figure A.5: Groups Displaying Outlier Behavior

Figure A.6: Interruption Color-coded Stability-Plasticity

Figure A.7: Dominance Color-coded Stability-Plasticity

Figure A.8: Leadership Color-coded Stability-Plasticity

Figure A.9: Openness Color-coded Stability-Plasticity

Figure A.10: Conscientiousness Color-coded Stability-Plasticity

Figure A.11: Extraversion Color-coded Stability-Plasticity

Figure A.12: Agreeableness Color-coded Stability-Plasticity

Figure A.13: Emotional Stability Color-coded Stability-Plasticity

Figure A.14: Stability-Plasticity: Four Randomly Sampled Points from Fitted 2D Gaussian Distribution

Figure A.15: Group Personality in the Stability-Plasticity Domain

Figure A.16: Interruption Color-coded Group Personality in the Stability-Plasticity Domain

Bibliography

- [1] Dairazalia Sanchez-Cortes et al. “A nonverbal behavior approach to identify emergent leaders in small groups”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia* 14.3 (2011), pp. 816–832.
- [2] Britta Wrede and Elizabeth Shriberg. “Spotting” hot spots” in meetings: human judgments and prosodic cues.” In: *INTERSPEECH*. Vol. 2003. 2003, pp. 2805–2808.
- [3] Gabriel Skantze. “Towards a general, continuous model of turn-taking in spoken dialogue using LSTM recurrent neural networks”. In: *Proceedings of the 18th Annual SIGdial Meeting on Discourse and Dialogue*. 2017, pp. 220–230.
- [4] Chi-Chun Lee and Shrikanth Narayanan. “Predicting interruptions in dyadic spoken interactions”. In: *2010 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*. IEEE. 2010, pp. 5250–5253.
- [5] Katherine Hilton. “The Perception of Overlapping Speech: Effects of Speaker Prosody and Listener Attitudes.” In: *Interspeech*. 2016, pp. 1260–1264.
- [6] DeLiang Wang and Jitong Chen. “Supervised speech separation based on deep learning: An overview”. In: *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing* 26.10 (2018), pp. 1702–1726.
- [7] Ariel Ephrat, Tavi Halperin, and Shmuel Peleg. “Improved speech reconstruction from silent video”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops*. 2017, pp. 455–462.
- [8] Aviv Gabbay et al. “Seeing through noise: Visually driven speaker separation and enhancement”. In: *2018 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE. 2018, pp. 3051–3055.

- [9] Ariel Ephrat et al. “Looking to listen at the cocktail party: A speaker-independent audio-visual model for speech separation”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.03619* (2018).
- [10] Triantafyllos Afouras, Joon Son Chung, and Andrew Zisserman. “The conversation: Deep audio-visual speech enhancement”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.04121* (2018).
- [11] Triantafyllos Afouras et al. “Self-supervised learning of audio-visual objects from video”. In: *Computer Vision–ECCV 2020: 16th European Conference, Glasgow, UK, August 23–28, 2020, Proceedings, Part XVIII 16*. Springer. 2020, pp. 208–224.
- [12] Aviv Gabbay, Asaph Shamir, and Shmuel Peleg. “Visual speech enhancement”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.08789* (2017).
- [13] Yuxuan Wang, Arun Narayanan, and DeLiang Wang. “On training targets for supervised speech separation”. In: *IEEE/ACM transactions on audio, speech, and language processing* 22.12 (2014), pp. 1849–1858.
- [14] Ziteng Wang et al. “Oracle performance investigation of the ideal masks”. In: *2016 IEEE International Workshop on Acoustic Signal Enhancement (IWAENC)*. IEEE. 2016, pp. 1–5.
- [15] Dong Yu et al. “Permutation invariant training of deep models for speaker-independent multi-talker speech separation”. In: *2017 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE. 2017, pp. 241–245.
- [16] Yao-Hung Hubert Tsai et al. “Multimodal transformer for unaligned multi-modal language sequences”. In: *Proceedings of the conference. Association for Computational Linguistics. Meeting*. Vol. 2019. NIH Public Access. 2019, p. 6558.
- [17] Zhuoran Shen et al. “Efficient attention: Attention with linear complexities”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*. 2021, pp. 3531–3539.
- [18] JCSJ Junior et al. “First impressions: A survey on computer vision-based apparent personality trait analysis”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.08046* (2018).

- [19] Florian Eyben et al. “The Geneva minimalistic acoustic parameter set (GeMAPS) for voice research and affective computing”. In: *IEEE transactions on affective computing* 7.2 (2015), pp. 190–202.
- [20] Florian Eyben, Martin Wöllmer, and Björn Schuller. “Opensmile: the munich versatile and fast open-source audio feature extractor”. In: *Proceedings of the 18th ACM international conference on Multimedia*. 2010, pp. 1459–1462.
- [21] Tadas Baltrušaitis, Marwa Mahmoud, and Peter Robinson. “Cross-dataset learning and person-specific normalisation for automatic action unit detection”. In: *2015 11th IEEE International Conference and Workshops on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition (FG)*. Vol. 6. IEEE. 2015, pp. 1–6.
- [22] Tadas Baltrusaitis et al. “Openface 2.0: Facial behavior analysis toolkit”. In: *2018 13th IEEE international conference on automatic face & gesture recognition (FG 2018)*. IEEE. 2018, pp. 59–66.
- [23] Olivia Wiles, A Koepke, and Andrew Zisserman. “Self-supervised learning of a facial attribute embedding from video”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1808.06882* (2018).
- [24] Jacob Devlin et al. “Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.04805* (2018).
- [25] Yinhan Liu et al. “Roberta: A robustly optimized bert pretraining approach”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.11692* (2019).
- [26] John M Digman. “Personality structure: Emergence of the five-factor model”. In: *Annual review of psychology* 41.1 (1990), pp. 417–440.
- [27] John M Digman. “Higher-order factors of the Big Five.” In: *Journal of personality and social psychology* 73.6 (1997), p. 1246.
- [28] Kerry L Jang et al. “Behavioral genetics of the higher-order factors of the Big Five”. In: *Personality and individual Differences* 41.2 (2006), pp. 261–272.
- [29] Colin G DeYoung, Jordan B Peterson, and Daniel M Higgins. “Higher-order factors of the Big Five predict conformity: Are there neuroses of health?” In: *Personality and Individual differences* 33.4 (2002), pp. 533–552.
- [30] Jacob B Hirsh, Colin G DeYoung, and Jordan B Peterson. “Metatraits of the Big Five differentially predict engagement and restraint of behavior”. In: *Journal of personality* 77.4 (2009), pp. 1085–1102.

- [31] Sigal G Barsade and Andrew P Knight. “Group affect”. In: *Annu. Rev. Organ. Psychol. Organ. Behav.* 2.1 (2015), pp. 21–46.
- [32] Chi-Chun Lee, Sungbok Lee, and Shrikanth S Narayanan. “An analysis of multimodal cues of interruption in dyadic spoken interactions”. In: *Ninth Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association*. 2008.
- [33] Hervé Bredin et al. “Pyannote. audio: neural building blocks for speaker diarization”. In: *ICASSP 2020-2020 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE. 2020, pp. 7124–7128.
- [34] Latané Bullock, Hervé Bredin, and Leibny Paola Garcia-Perera. “Overlap-aware diarization: resegmentation using neural end-to-end overlapped speech detection”. In: *ICASSP 2020, IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*. Barcelona, Spain, 2020.
- [35] Iain McCowan et al. “The AMI meeting corpus”. In: *Proceedings of the 5th international conference on methods and techniques in behavioral research*. Vol. 88. Citeseer. 2005, p. 100.
- [36] Mirco Ravanelli and Yoshua Bengio. “Speaker recognition from raw waveform with sincnet”. In: *2018 IEEE Spoken Language Technology Workshop (SLT)*. IEEE. 2018, pp. 1021–1028.
- [37] Neal B Gallagher, Donal O’Sullivan, and Manuel Palacios. “The Effect of Data Centering on PCA Models”. In: (2020).
- [38] Leland McInnes, John Healy, and James Melville. “Umap: Uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.03426* (2018).
- [39] Natalie J Allen and Thomas A O’Neill. “The trajectory of emergence of shared group-level constructs”. In: *Small Group Research* 46.3 (2015), pp. 352–390.
- [40] Gregg Willcox et al. “Measuring group personality with swarm AI”. In: *2019 First International Conference on Transdisciplinary AI (TransAI)*. IEEE. 2019, pp. 10–17.
- [41] Shun-Chang Zhong et al. “Predicting Group Performances Using a Personality Composite-Network Architecture During Collaborative Task.” In: *INTERSPEECH*. 2019, pp. 1676–1680.

List of Figures

A.1	Interruption Color-coded UMAP of Speaker Averages	24
A.2	Dominance Color-coded UMAP of Speaker Averages	24
A.3	Leadership Color-coded UMAP of Speaker Averages	25
A.4	KMeans Clustering of UMAP Projected Speaker Averages	25
A.5	Groups Displaying Outlier Behavior	26
A.6	Interruption Color-coded Stability-Plasticity	27
A.7	Dominance Color-coded Stability-Plasticity	27
A.8	Leadership Color-coded Stability-Plasticity	27
A.9	Openness Color-coded Stability-Plasticity	28
A.10	Conscientiousness Color-coded Stability-Plasticity	28
A.11	Extraversion Color-coded Stability-Plasticity	28
A.12	Agreeableness Color-coded Stability-Plasticity	29
A.13	Emotional Stability Color-coded Stability-Plasticity	29
A.14	Stability-Plasticity: Four Randomly Sampled Points from Fitted 2D Gaussian Distribution	29
A.15	Group Personality in the Stability-Plasticity Domain	30
A.16	Interruption Color-coded Group Personality in the Stability-Plasticity Domain . .	31